

NOTES

and at very high concentration of sulphuric acid (18*N*) through steps (ii) and (iii), both of which are two electron transfer steps. The net reaction in the latter case then corresponds to

In the reverse case, when hydrazine is added to permanganate, hydrazoic acid with a very high oxidation potential ($E^\circ = 3 \cdot 09$)¹⁶ stands little chance of being formed as long as permanganate is in excess and the single inflexion that occurs at 2.0 moles hydrazine per mole permanganate is consistent with the single one-equivalent oxidation step (i) leading to the formation of nitrogen and ammonia.

TABLE 4. 0.0937 (*M*) HYDRAZINE SOLUTION ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.0016 (*M*) DICHROMATE SOLUTION, TEMP. 30°; REACTION MIXTURES STORED FOR 72 HR.

H ₂ SO ₄ concentrations (approx.)	Point of inflexions (in ml. of N ₂ H ₄)	Moles of hydrazine per mole of dichromate
0.2 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
1 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
2 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
3 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
4 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
6 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
8 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4

When dichromate is gradually added to hydrazine, single inflexion occurs at 0.66 moles of dichromate per mole of hydrazine in all cases (0.2*N* to 8*N* sulphuric acid media). This means that the oxidation proceeds exclusively through two equivalent steps of the type (ii).

The stoichiometry does not change with changes in either reactant concentrations or mineral acid concentrations. In view of these, this reaction may be considered to be analytically significant.

In the reverse case, inflexion occurs at 2.4 moles of hydrazine per mole of dichromate consistent with the equation,

indicating that the reaction proceeds more through two equivalent steps of the type (ii) than through (i).

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A Convenient Method for Chlorination of Ketones

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THE chlorination of ketones to date^{1,2,3} involves the preparation first of hypochlorite compound or the passage of chlorine gas separately generated into the solution of the compound. Both of these procedures are more time consuming and inconvenient. We were interested in the preparation of the chloro derivatives of the compound I_a and I_b, C.D. studies of which prompted us to look for a convenient method for the chlorination.

Compound I_a or I_b when dissolved in acetic acid and to which almost double the molar quantities of HCl and H₂O₂ were added at 5°-10°, gave after work up almost 80-85% of the yield of the 6-chloro derivatives (I_c & I_d). The elemental analysis and N.M.R. spectrum support the structures I_c & I_d. N.M.R. spectra in addition to the reported pattern of the compounds⁴ shows two doublets (1 proton each) centred at 5.75 δ and 2.45 δ with a coupling constant of 7 cps. This would be in agreement with the trans coupling⁵ of the two hydrogen at C₅ & C₆. Further I_c & I_d on treatment with zinc dust and acetic acid gives the corresponding amines I_e & I_f, the structures of which were confirmed by their I.R.

spectra and elemental analysis. Chlorination of acetophenone under the similar conditions gives ω -chloro acetophenone in 84% yield. Authenticity of the compound was confirmed by the mixed m.p. with an authentic sample. 7-Oxomethyl-O-methyl podocarpate also provided a good yield of the 6-chloro derivative, which showed characteristic doublets as in I_a & I_b with a coupling constant of 7 cps.

- I_a R = R' = H, R'' = NO₂
 I_b R = R' = H, R'' = NO₂
 I_c R'' = H, R = Cl, R' = NO₂
 I_d R' = H, R = Cl, R'' = NO₂
 I_e R = R'' = H, R' = NH₂
 I_f R = R' = H, R'' = NH₂
 I_g R' = R'' = H, R = Cl.

Experimental

1. 6-Chloro-7-oxo-11-nitro methyl-o-methyl podocarpate :

Compound I_b (1 gm) was dissolved in acetic acid (30 ml), H₂O₂ (5 ml) and conc. HCl (5 ml) were added into the solution and the mixture was kept at 5°-10° for the whole night. The mixture was then poured over ice and triturated. White solid obtained was filtered off, washed with water, dried and crystallized from methanol, m.p. 171°. Yield 880 mg (80%). (Found : C, 57.22; H, 5.62; N, 3.30; Cl, 9.10. C₁₉H₂₂NO₄ requires C, 57.65; H, 5.56; N, 3.54; Cl, 8.98%.)

2. 6-Chloro-7-oxo-13-nitro-methyl-o-methyl podocarpate :

Compound, I_a (1 gm) was dissolved in acetic acid (150 ml). H₂O₂ (10 ml) and HCl (10 ml) were added into the solution and the mixture was kept at 5°-10° for the whole night. The mixture was then poured over ice and triturated. White solid obtained was filtered off, washed with water, dried and extracted with solvent ether. The undissolved product was filtered off, washed with ether and dried, m.p. 242°-43° (500 mg). Mixed m.p. with the starting compound showed no depression.

Ether extract was dried completely and the solid obtained was crystallized from methanol. White needles m.p. 186°. Yield 350 mg (65%). (Found : Cl, 8.80; C₁₉H₂₂NO₄ requires Cl, 8.98%.)

3. 6-Chloro-7-oxo-methyl-o-methyl podocarpate :

Keto ester, I_g (1 gm) was dissolved in dichloromethane (4 ml) and methanol (2 ml). The reaction mixture was treated with H₂O₂ (5 ml) and conc. HCl (1 ml) and was kept at the room temperature overnight. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over magnesium sulphate and ether was evaporated completely to give 0.92 g of yellow oily product which was crystallized from methanol to give a colourless crystalline product, m.p. 119°. Yield 0.750 g (68%). (Found : Cl, 9.60; C₁₉H₂₃ClO₄ requires Cl, 10.01%.)

4. ω -Chloro Acetophenone :

Acetophenone (10.20 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (25 ml). H₂O₂ (5 ml) and conc. HCl (5 ml) were added into the solution and the mixture was kept at 5°-10° for the whole night. The mixture was then poured over ice and the white solid obtained was washed with water, dried and crystallized from petroleum ether, m.p. 54°. Yield 11.0 g (84%).

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Physicochemical Studies of the Co(II) and Ni(II) Chelates of Sodio Benzene-sulphonate Azo *P*-Cresol

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THE azedye-sodio benzene sulphonate-azo-*p*-cresol has been synthesized by the authors. The stoichiometry of the complexes of Co(II) and Ni(II) has been investigated. The chelate contains metal and metal ligand in the ratio of 1 : 1. The stability constants of the cobalt and nickel complexes are found as 8.237×10^8 and 1.139×10^8 respectively.